

The Role of Advertisement in Product Promotions - An Overview

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Abstract

Advertising is a famous feature of modern business operations. One can encounter advertising messages while watching TV, reading magazines, listening to the radio, surfing the internet, or even simply while walking down the street, as advertisement has a stimulating influence on the purchasing behavior of the customer. Products or services need the support of well-devised schemes of promotion. Producers must have a good idea to plan how they can promote their selling with leaflets, advertisements in many Media. This mammoth surge of advertisements from every possible source is basically to fulfill the urge of marketers to reach to a large number of people so that their product may receive optimum exposure. A rounded marketing plan should include an appropriate mix of promotion. In sales promotion mixture should rely not only on advertising but advertisement occupied a major part. This paper examines the process of advertisements in moving the product in the good position in the market. There are many sales promotion tool adopted by the marketer among them advertisement play a major role to bring the product in top position. The study also tries to examine the growth pattern and trend of advertisement. Further, it seeks to evaluate the effectiveness of advertisement expenses on sales of selected companies operating in India at aggregate and disaggregate levels. The article highlights the role of advertisement in product promotions.

Keywords: Advertising, sales promotion and product position, Medias, Brand image.

Introduction

Nowadays people are conscious to look for the best one and that's why their fluctuating mind may switch on to new brands with a simple stimulus. Know your customers and give them what they want is the fundamental principle of marketing. Consumer behavior refers to the selection, purchase and consumption of goods and services for the satisfaction of their wants. In this case, an extra incentive can be added to a product by different promotional activities. Again it is remarkable that a product lack of any significant advantage can be made it difficult to create an advertising campaign which can be used to make people try the product. Today the marketers are confused to take up the appropriate marketing strategy due to a variety of products, increased customer's expectation and rapid industrial growth. In this situation, it comes into view that some marketers are not considerate of different promotional activities and advertising where some others use these unconsciously. Advertising can be utilized for creating

awareness and promoting one of the services or for services of all the departments. A thorough analysis is required to decide on the objectives of a particular advertising campaign. Television is the major medium of advertisements. When a firm wants to throw its point or product to the public, this is the most effective means of doing it. Secondly, press advertisements seem to be effective among people who look for certified advertisements. The newspapers provide certified ads and it depends on the presentation of the ads, i.e., its captions and color effects should impress the customers. Radio ads must be clear and audible. These are all means for motivating factors for influencing customer buying behavior. So it is the time to rethink the actual effects of advertising on the customer's mind. An advertisement has always been a part of the industrial marketing process and it is the preferred tool used to reach customers. The allocation of the marketing budget is now reallocating with the advertising budget, and that indicates the importance of advertisement. The aim of the study is to be clear, as a marketer, what effects of advertising have on customers buying behavior by analyzing practical and theoretical evidence. However the results obtained from the research work is also self-describable.

Review of Previous Literature

Rodge (2001) finds that the rural consumers attach more importance to the advertisement and its impact as compared to urban. He also pointed out that rural consumers are more influenced by electronic media than print media.

Arens (2002) said that Advertisements tend to be highly informative & present the customer with some important product attributes or features that will lead to favorable attitudes and can be used as the basis for rational brand preference. People get information from the advertisement through the attractiveness it holds, the attention it creates and the awareness it gives.

John and Slater (2003) suggested that the advertisement must do more than simply communicating information. The advertising must reinforce what consumers already know and feel about the brand and strengthen their resolve that they consistently make the right choice by buying it. The advertisement strengthens their attachment to the brand by depicting pride, satisfaction, positive experiences, strong user imagery, and strong brand personality.

Tellis (2004) summarized the advertising literature by explaining that advertising effects can be classified as either behavioral or attitudinal. Behavioral effects act instantaneously, at the moment of exposure, or shortly reafter that. Attitudinal effects operate by changing the consumer's attitudes and memory over a longer period. Using this simple dichotomy, prior research has categorized ads into those that predominantly seek a behavioral response and those that predominantly seek to influence attitudes.

Prasad and Nataraj (2006) in their article, "Why to Exhibit at an exhibition" observed that marketing and advertising today had become as important as manufacturing and production due to the increasing competition and awareness among consumers.

Petrovici and et al. (2007) found out the perceived socio-economic effects of advertising and consumer beliefs and attitudes toward advertising in Bulgaria and Romania. According to them, there is a common belief (more than 80 percent) that advertising promotes undesirable values and messages.

Need for the Study

Firms are spending a huge amount of their budget on advertising their products and services. They are investing to influence the buying behavior of customers and determining the factors that have direct or indirect effects on buying behavior like purchasing power. This focus on advertising is because it is considered an effective tool to motivate customers and influence their buying

behaviour. Advertisers hope that their ads will change the buying behavior of the target market and customers will buy their products. To make their advertising campaign even more effective and rewarding, advertisers are trying to analyze various factors which may influence customers' buying behavior e.g., residential area lifestyle, education and purchasing power, etc. For this purpose, as mentioned advertisers apply the hierarchy of effects model to expose brand cognition, where attitude leads towards actual purchasing.

Statement of the Problem

Advertising in general, the quality of products, service, application, etc. have also been highlighted. The products are not Expected quality, service and advantages when the consumer bought and consumed through advertisements. So the consumer feels that cheated by advertisement. The customer is reluctant to the purchase of goods and services through faith in the advertisement. There are numerous advertisements in Medias; television, radio, newspapers, and magazines but, the important question for a marketer is "do all these advertisements positively influence the customers brand preference?" If the advertisement is not created any positive change in customers brand preference, all the resources such as money, time and efforts spent on the advertisement will go in vain. Therefore, it is essential for a marketer to find out the extent to which the advertisement creates Positive change in preferring the brand of the company. In this context, the researcher to undertake research, advertisement effects on customers purchasing attitude.

Objectives of the Study

The following objectives are framed for the present study

- To study the role of advertisement in making awareness among customers in Cuddalore district.
- To evaluate the function of advertisements in brand positioning and brand loyalty.
- To analysis the impact advertisement effect on the purchase of the products in the study area.
- To review the customers' opinion regarding advertisements.

Hypothesis

H01: There is no significant difference between the demographic profile of the respondents and the role of advertisements in creating awareness.

H02: There is no significant difference between the demographic profile of the respondents and functions of advertisements in product positioning and brand loyalty.

H03: There is no significant difference between the demographic profile of the respondents and the impact of advertisements on the purchase of products.

H04: There is no significant difference between the demographic profile of the respondents and to review the customers' opinion regarding the advertisement.

Research Methodology

The approach of this paper work was a deductive approach. The paper covers only primary data which were collected through questionnaires. All of the respondents in this study are customers. Some well-designed questionnaires were administered to 600 customers constituting the sample size. After collecting primary data, some data are focused, selected, simplified. Then some reduced data are organized which make it easier to e conclude. Some hypotheses were placed corresponding to each question area which was also justified with suitable tools. The limitation of the present study is it mainly focused on the short-term effects of advertising on the customers' behavior.

The present study also shows that the relationship between age and consumer preference on the

mode of advertisement. It is observed that consumer preference on the mode of advertisement. 20-30 years age group consumer prefers television advertisement mostly. Most of the 30-40 years age group consumer prefers the advertisements in press and print media. More percent of 40-50 years age group consumer prefers radio and another mode of advertisements. Ultimately this shows that all age group of customers are more conscious about advertisement and its impact on their preference.

The mass media is the powerful media to the companies to create awareness about the availability of the products in the market. It is also found that the highest percentage of customers that is 47 percent knew about the product through television, 31 percent known through newspapers and other print media. The customers were aware of other sources at 16 percent that is through interactions with their friends, relatives, colleagues etc. Nowadays the internet also has the power to create awareness among customers. But the user of the internet sources is very marginal due to lack of technical skills. Hence it is inferred that the television and newspapers are the cheapest sources of awareness about the products to customers.

The present study analyzed the effects of advertising on customers buying behavior all the aforementioned observation were tested. From the survey, it was found that advertising position a product or service strongly in the mind of the consumer to encourage the repeated purchase of the product. From the analysis the calculated chi-square value is more than the actual value, so the hypothesis of an advertisement does not any influences in changing the buying behavior of customers is rejected. It is concluded that there is a significant influence of advertisement in customers buying behavior and advertisers create some special moments that will resonate the mind of the target customer and motivate the audience to purchase the advertised product.

Sampling Design

The target population for data collection is the customers in the study area. As the selected area of the study is the Cuddalore district, an attempt is made to distinguish the district into different strata. The stratification is done by geographical and administrative factors. Cuddalore district constitutes three revenue divisions: Cuddalore, Chidambaram and Vrindhachalam, divided into six taluks, namely, Cuddalore, Panruti, Vrindhachalam, Tittakuti, Chidambaram and Kattumannar Koil. To collect primary data for the study, the multi-stage sampling technique is adopted. At the first stage, all the three revenue divisions are selected. In the second stage, three taluks (Cuddalore, Vrindhachalam, and Chidambaram) out of the six taluks are selected purposely from the three revenue divisions, i.e., one taluk from each division. In the final stage, from each of the selected taluk, modest samples of 200 are selected randomly from 100 respondents each taluk in rural and 100 respondents each taluk urban having the sample size of 600 customers.

Statistical Tools

The collected primary data are subjected to various statistical techniques from descriptive statistics like Mean, and Standard deviation, co-efficient of variation, t-test for independent samples, One way ANOVA, chi-square test, KMO and Bartlett's Test, Multivariate techniques such as Factor Analysis were used.

Advertisement Effects on Customers Purchasing Attitude

This section is devoted to testing the significant difference between respondents demographic variables (age, educational qualification, occupation, marital status, size of the family, nature of the family, and monthly income) concerning the advertisement effects on customers purchasing attitude. The following null hypothesis has been formulated

H01: There is no significant difference between the demographic profile of the respondents and the role of advertisements in creating awareness.

H02: There is no significant difference between the demographic profile of the respondents and functions of advertisements in product positioning and brand loyalty.

H03: There is no significant difference between the demographic profile of the respondents and the impact of advertisements on the purchase of products

H04: There is no significant difference between the demographic profile of the respondents and to review the customers' opinion regarding the advertisement.

One way ANOVA was applied to ascertain if there were any significant differences between respondents.

Age groups e concerning advertisements effects on customers purchasing attitude (role of advertisement in creating awareness, functions of advertisements in product positioning and brand loyalty, and the impact of advertisement on the purchase of products). The following null hypothesis has been formulated.

Table 1 ANOVA for Age and Advertisement Effects on Customers Purchasing Attitude

Age		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error of Mean	F-value	Sig.
Role of advertisement in creating awareness	Up to 20 years	83	60.39	7.467	0.820	8.284	0.001
	21 to 30 years	145	60.14	5.781	0.480		
	31 to 40 years	186	56.22	8.642	0.634		
	41 to 50 years	125	58.92	6.406	0.573		
	Above 50 years	61	58.34	5.636	0.722		
	Total	600	58.52	7.295	0.298		
Functions of advertisement in product positioning and brand loyalty	Up to 20 years	83	112.98	16.695	1.833		
	21 to 30 years	145	112.55	13.483	1.120		
	31 to 40 years	186	108.77	16.874	1.237	2.655	0.001
	41 to 50 years	125	113.24	10.400	0.930		
	Above 50 years	61	112.33	9.266	1.186		
	Total	600	111.56	14.296	0.584		
Impact of advertisements	Up to 20 years	83	52.29	8.415	0.924	8.603	0.001
	21 to 30 years	145	52.66	7.131	0.592		
	31 to 40 years	186	48.65	9.483	0.695		
	41 to 50 years	125	48.54	5.665	0.507		
	Above 50 years	61	50.90	5.331	0.683		
	Total	600	50.33	7.913	0.323		

Source: Computed from Primary Data

Role of Advertisement in Creating Awareness

The obtained „F value is 8.284 and it is significant at the 5 percent level. The value indicates that there is a significant difference between age group and the role of advertisement in creating awareness. Hence, the formulated hypothesis H0:2b “there is no significant difference between the age group of the respondents and the role of advertisement in creating awareness” is rejected. Further, the mean indicates that respondents of up to 20 years scored higher mean value of 60.39

and the lowest mean score of 58.34 was obtained by respondents with age. Above 50 years. This shows that the respondents of less than 20 years of age have more awareness of the role of advertisements.

Functions of Advertisements in Product Positioning and Brand Loyalty

The obtained „F value is 2.655, and it is significant at the 5 percent level. The value indicates that there is a significant difference between the age group and functions of advertisement in product positioning and brand loyalty. Hence, the formulated hypothesis H0:3b “there is no significant difference between the age group of the respondents and functions of advertisements in product positioning and brand loyalty.” Further, the mean indicates that respondents of up 41 to 50 years scored higher mean value of 113.24 and the lowest mean score of 108.77 was obtained by respondents with the age group of 31 to 40 years. This shows the functions of advertisement in brand positioning and brand loyalty is more among the age group of 31 to 40 years of the respondents.

Impact of Advertisements on the Purchase of Products

The obtained „F value is 8.603 and it is significant at the 5 percent level. The value indicates that there is a significant difference between the age group and impact of advertisements on the purchase of products. Hence, the formulated hypothesis H0:4b “there is no significant difference between the age group of the respondents and “impact of advertisements on the purchase of products” is rejected. Further, the mean indicates that respondents of up 21 to 30 years scored higher mean value of 52.66 and the lowest mean score of 48.54 was obtained by respondents with the age group of 41 to 50 years. This shows the impact of advertisement is more among the age group of 21 to 30 years of the respondents.

Suggestions and Recommendations

- The study also found that television advertising is effective in reach and creation of awareness among the respondents and recommends that the advertiser should be used more in television advertising to increase their market share and provide product information.
- Most of the respondents think that advertisements do not give the true picture of the products advertised.
- Hence, it is suggested that the advertiser or companies should present the necessary information to attract the customers.
- The study suggests that most of the male customers like the advertisements as compared to female customers, so the companies or the advertiser should take the necessary steps to take to attract the female customers through advertisement.
- The advertisements have a strong positive influence and significant relationship with customers buying behavior. People perceive the advertisement with the positive attitude. Study depicted that customers are more conscious about their social status, so they prefer advertised products and affects the customers purchasing attitude positively.
- Advertisement convinces the people to use the product at least once in their lives. Most of the people rely on advertisements rather than other sources like family, friends and reference groups opinions regarding the product.
- Advertisement can affect people at any income level but it has no greater influence on expensive products. In the present scenario, companies cannot sell their products or services without advertisements.

Conclusion

This study was taken to cover the moderate and high-income groups and also people belonging to such groups are well educated. The study has demonstrated using some advanced questionnaires and hypotheses that the advertising has an ambiguous impact on consumer behavior. It is of vital importance to know the long-term effects of advertisement on the customer's purchase behavior. Among the selected respondents for the present study press and television advertisements get the highest position because most of the housewives and retired people find time to read write-ups and enjoy the television advertisements. The working youth says lack of time is the main factor influencing them in choosing the mode of advertisement, and hence they afford to mass and conclude advertisements are well accepted and recognized by people depending up their effectiveness in putting across product and services in an acceptable form. Hence advertisements can be made effective by understanding what the people want and what they look forward to from a product or service.

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